

Application form: Open Science Infrastructure (2024) - full proposal

Public version – financials adjusted to exclude HR/personnel details

Section 1: Applicants

Name of the main applicant	dr. Hannes Datta
Affiliation – institution	Tilburg University, Tilburg School of Economics and Management (TiSEM)
Affiliation – department	Department of Marketing
Position	Associate Professor
End date of contract	Permanent position
Guarantee needed & added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
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Name of the co-applicant	dr. Tom Emery
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus University
Affiliation – department	Department of Public Administration and Sociology
Position	Associate Professor & Executive Director of <u>ODISSEI</u> (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations; the Dutch National Research Infrastructure for the Social Sciences)
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Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
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Name of the co-applicant	dr. Ana Martinovici
Affiliation – institution	Erasmus University, Rotterdam School of Management
Affiliation – department	Department of Marketing Management
Position	Assistant Professor
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Guarantee added yes/no/n.a.	n.a.
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Organisation	University of Melbourne, Australia

Section 2: Summary

Proposed project title	ReproHub: Enhanced Replicability and Open Science Education for Research with Secondary and Sensitive Data
Project duration (in months)	48 months

English public summary

Despite continuous investments into open science infrastructure, research materials—like data and code—are hard to find, and even experts struggle to reproduce research results. ReproHub addresses these challenges with four deliverables to support researchers and other stakeholders in finding, documenting, and verifying research output: ReproBuddy (an AI tool to improve reproducibility packages), ReproRun (a system to validate results), OpenScienceRadar (a browser extension making open resources more visible), and OpenScienceHub.nl (a platform with accessible educational material). By building on ODISSEI and Tilburg Science Hub—two Dutch open science infrastructure components—ReproHub seeks to strengthen transparency and public trust in science.

Word count EN-SUM (max 100): 100

Dutch public summary

Ondanks investeringen in open science blijft onderzoeksmateriaal lastig vindbaar en zijn onderzoeksresultaten zelfs voor experts moeilijk te reproduceren. ReproHub pakt deze uitdagingen aan met vier nieuwe tools die onderzoekers en andere belanghebbenden ondersteunen bij het vinden, documenteren en verifiëren van onderzoeksresultaten: ReproBuddy (AI-tool voor verbetering van de repliceerbaarheid van onderzoek), ReproRun (systeem voor resultaatvalidatie), OpenScienceRadar (browserextensie die de zichtbaarheid van open wetenschappelijke bronnen vergroot) en OpenScienceHub.nl (platform met educatief materiaal). Door voort te bouwen op ODISSEI en Tilburg Science Hub—twee onderdelen van de Nederlandse open science infrastructuur—draagt dit project bij aan transparantie en het publieke vertrouwen in wetenschap.

Word count NL-SUM (max 100): 100

Section 3: Alignment with the scope of the call

3.1 Vision for the project and alignment with the aim of this call

Adoption of open science (OS) practices among social scientists has doubled over the past decade, reflecting a growing focus on **transparency** and **reproducibility** (Ferguson et al. 2023). Yet, significant challenges remain: research outputs—especially in secondary data-intensive disciplines—often do not reproduce (Hardwicke et al. 2022; Trisovic et al. 2022), and OS materials—e.g., code and data—remain fragmented or largely invisible (Cadwallader and Hrynaszkiewicz 2022; Katz and Hong 2024).

ReproHub addresses these challenges by building a federated **OS infrastructure** extending existing solutions: **ODISSEI** (**O**pen **D**ata **I**nfrastructure for **S**ocial **S**cience and **E**conomic **I**nnovations), a Dutch data and compute platform involving 45+ research institutions, and **Tilburg Science Hub (TSH)**—a global educational resource with 450,000 visitors annually. Specifically, ReproHub enhances (inter)national OS infrastructure with four key deliverables: (1) **improving the quality of replication packages** with an AI-assistant (*ReproBuddy*), (2) enabling **research results verification at scale** (*ReproRun*), (3) making fragmented **OS output discoverable** alongside search results in academic search engines (*OpenScienceRadar*), and (4) lowering the **entry barriers to OS adoption** through Open Educational Resources (OER) and community engagement (*opensciencehub.nl*).

In line with the **National Programme Open Science** (2022, 4.4/4.7), ReproHub promotes accessibility and adoption through education, integration, federation, and engagement.

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3.2 User communities, challenges and needs

Reproducibility and verifiability are essential for **public trust in science** and to reduce research waste, like unused code or data. To meet these standards, institutions increasingly require researchers to submit reproducibility packages, often checked manually by **university data stewards, journal editors, or ODISSEI staff**. This process is error-prone and not scalable—even experts struggle to document their research sufficiently well.

ReproBuddy (WP1) will offer **researchers** context-aware guidance using an open-source Large Language Model (LLM) fine-tuned using curated reproducibility guidelines. *ReproRun* (WP2), in turn, is a workflow for **secure and automated results validation**. Just as institutions like VeriSign issue “certificates” to show websites are safe, *ReproRun* enables **institutions** to issue trusted certificates for reproducibility. Initially integrated in ODISSEI’s Secure Analysis Environment (*SANE*), *ReproRun* can be adopted by **researchers, universities, funders, the Dutch IT cooperative of education and research (SURF)**, and ultimately, the **European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)**.

Recent decades saw significant investments in OS, yet **user communities** struggle to navigate a **fragmented OS landscape**. While academic search engines simplify publication searches, they often do not cross-link to code and data on platforms like **ODISSEI** or **Zenodo**—limiting the findability, reuse, and impact of OS materials. *OpenScienceRadar* (WP3), a browser plugin, will directly provide these cross-links in academic search engines and on publisher pages, helping **(PhD) students, researchers, and library personnel** discover open materials.

Finally, widespread adoption of OS requires **accessible education**. With *TSH*—including its “snackable” tutorials and search-engine-optimized (SEO) content—the project will **scale an OS community of researchers, support staff, and (PhD) students**. *TSH* will relaunch as *opensciencehub.nl* (WP4), opening OS infrastructure (e.g., ODISSEI’s *SANE*) to a broader audience. ODISSEI, in turn, will embed content in existing infrastructure, serving accessible documentation directly to its users.

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3.3 Alignment of project with OS principles

Reproducibility concerns remain an important challenge. For Dutch research involving Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) data alone, **ODISSEI** estimates **±800 projects per year** are difficult to reproduce. Fragmentation and usability concerns, in turn, hinder the adoption of OS, as research funder NWO highlights (NWO 2025).

The Netherlands has repeatedly committed to addressing these challenges, reflected in **policies and roadmaps at national and international levels**, including the NPOS2030 Ambition Document, the Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2018), the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (2023), and ADORE (2024). *ReproHub* supports these national and international ambitions by making reproducibility more time-efficient, user-friendly, and broadly accessible. It promotes the **visibility and adoption of a wide range of OS practices** and fosters **reproducible and verifiable research workflows at scale**.

The development of *ReproHub's* four deliverables reflects OS principles. Built using a **transparent governance structure** (public repository, defined processes, archived at OpenAIRE's Zenodo), **open-source technologies, and open software packages**, all components will be **FAIR** (Barker et al. 2022) (see also section 5.2). The project extends **ODISSEI infrastructure**—including ODISSEI's **Portal**, **SoDa (Social Data Analytics)**, the **Code Library**, and **SANE** on **SURF Research Cloud (SRC)**. It combines the expertise of **ODISSEI** (OS infrastructure) and **TSH** (OER) with the complementary methodological insights from OS experts, including researchers, information specialists, and infrastructure developers, adhering to **community standards on FAIR principles, replication formats, and data dictionaries**. By separating analytical workflows from sensitive data using **differential privacy principles** (Dwork & Roth, 2014), the developed tools will also be relevant for research fields like healthcare.

Collectively, *ReproHub's* deliverables equip researchers, funders, and publishers with the **tools and documentation to meet OS standards**, strengthening **integrity and public trust** in research at a time of **increasing scrutiny and systemic reproducibility concerns**.

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3.4 Access policy

All resources will be **open access**, published on **GitHub** under appropriate permissive licenses and archived on Zenodo, ensuring FAIR-compliance. *ReproHub's* four deliverables will be developed for deployment and adaptation by users or institutions on their **own infrastructure or SANE via SRC**, depending on data protection needs.

The project also includes **hosted services**, with costs budgeted during the duration of the project and a sustainability plan for after, covering:

- (1) A publicly available website, serving OER developed in WP4 at *opensciencehub.nl*, and making accessible all tools from WP1-WP3.
- (2) *ReproBuddy* (WP1) will be accessible via **SURFconext login**, starting with Tilburg and Erasmus University. Other Dutch institutions may negotiate access or host a stand-alone version. Tilburg University and ODISSEI will evaluate access requests based on affiliation, capacity, and alignment.
- (3) A **database with a publicly accessible API** for *OpenScienceRadar* (WP3), a free browser plugin linking to OS materials.

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3.5 (Inter)national ecosystem

ReproHub adds value to the **national and international OS ecosystem** by filling a critical infrastructural gap: enabling reproducibility certification, even when working with restricted or proprietary data. It **extends existing OS platforms**—**ODISSEI** and **TSH**—and creates **synergies with international infrastructure**. By aligning with the **National Roadmap for Large-Scale Research Infrastructures, thematic digital competence centers (TDCCs)**, and **EOSC**, *ReproHub* strengthens integration with the broader (inter)national **OS ecosystem** and enables reuse. For example, by documentation in **CERIE** (Common European Research Information Format) and **SSHOC** (Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud), *ReproHub's* tools become discoverable through the **EOSC**.

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ReproHub promotes **community uptake** through partnering with local (Tilburg/Erasmus) and national (OSC-NL) **OS Communities (OSC)**. In addition, we seek integration with (inter)national projects such as **CODECHECK** (manual code checks), **The Turing Way**, **SIPS** (Society for the Improvement of Psychological Science), and the **Institute for Replication (i4R)**, ensuring interoperability and avoiding duplication while fostering a **scalable and open research environment**. We are already in active dialogue with **FORRT** (Framework for Open and Reproducible Research Training) and **Research Transparency Check** (transparency check for publications).

Word count SEC35 (max. 200): 200

Section 4: Feasibility

4.1 Project plan

Workflow and Methods

ReproHub follows agile development cycles, continuous user testing, and phased integration across six work packages (WPs, see Figure 1):

- WPs 1–4 define technical requirements for *ReproHub*'s four deliverables:
 - *ReproBuddy* (AI-improved reproducibility packages),
 - *ReproRun* (validation/provenance workflows),
 - *OpenScienceRadar* (OS visibility), and
 - *OpenScienceHub* (OER and community engagement).
- WP5 is the project's "technical engine". A developer pool, including Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and student assistants (SAs), implements technical solutions from WP1-4, maintains Kubernetes environments, CI/CD pipelines, and APIs.
- WP6 manages governance and coordination, with a project manager (PM) overseeing compliance, reporting, and communication.

Inspired by practices at TSH, the team meets bi-weekly to share progress and address bottlenecks.

Figure 1

Timeline, Outputs, and Activities

WP1–4 follow three phases, providing a structured yet flexible progression: prototyping (Months 1–18, co-design with users), expansion (Months 19–36, leadership engagement, co-design with ODISSEI network), and embedding (Months 37–48, community contributions & wider adoption).

The collaboration between members of WP1-4 and WP5 ensures that the infrastructure meets quality standards and researchers' needs. With minimal dependencies and clearly defined roles, especially between WP1-4 and WP5, outputs and activities are detailed next.

WP 1:	ReproBuddy (Months 1 - 48)
Personnel:	Martinovici (lead), Vossen, SA1
Consortium partners:	Deer, ODISSEI , Digital Research Support (DRS) Tilburg
Goals:	Build an AI-assistant to improve reproducibility packages.
Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define user interaction and curate reproducibility guidelines Engineer prompts and validate LLM output Specify/run user testing
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Tool provides feedback on content and structure of packages Phase 2: Enhanced feedback, based on package maturity and users' infrastructural needs Phase 3: Enhanced feedback, adaptable to journal/university policies
WP 2:	ReproRun (Months 1 – 48)
Personnel:	Klein (lead), Van Lissa
Consortium partners:	ODISSEI
Goals:	Build an automated workflow for validating and documenting results provenance.
Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop workflow for validating results Define technical approach for generating verification certificates Create execution templates and test workflows
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Workflow available with certification of research results Phase 2: Standard Docker templates (e.g., R, Python) + customizable templates available Phase 3: Workflow integrated (ODISSEI's SANE and EOSC)
WP 3:	OpenScienceRadar (Months 1 – 48)
Personnel:	Wichmann (lead), Datta, SA2
Consortium partners:	ODISSEI , Tilburg University Library
Goals:	Increase OS visibility with a browser plugin.
Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Catalogue existing OS indicators and databases Define database/API and implement integration. Evaluate impact on views of OS resources Coordinate rollout strategy nationally (start with Tilburg and Rotterdam)
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: Existing browser extension displays OS content, starting with ODISSEI Knowledge Graph Phase 2: Extension released via browser stores; impact on downloads of ODISSEI OS materials assessed Phase 3: Further indicators integrated; adoption across the Netherlands
WP 4:	OpenScienceHub (Months 1 – 48)
Personnel:	Banerjee (lead), SA3, SA4, Lemmens
Consortium partners:	ODISSEI , Tilburg University Library
Goals:	Expand TSH nationally and document ODISSEI and OS infrastructure.
Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Specify backend needs and redesigned interface for <i>opensciencehub.nl</i> Guide and execute FAIR and SEO-optimized content creation Organize community onboarding, training and outreach
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1: OSH launched with improved visibility/usability; ODISSEI content available Phase 2: Content shared via ODISSEI channels; community-building launched Phase 3: Contributor tools added; platform integrated with Tilburg and Rotterdam research support

WP 5:	Infrastructure & Tooling (Months 1 – Months 48)
Personnel:	van Gils (lead), RSE1, RSE2 (Kirsch), SA5, SA6, Datta
Consortium partners:	IT infrastructure (Tilburg University) , ODISSEI
Goals:	Operate developer pool to support infrastructure development for WP1-WP4.
Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Setup and maintain Kubernetes cluster (WP1, WP3-4) • Deploy & fine-tune open-source LLM (WP1) • Build (WP1, WP3) and revise (WP4) user interfaces • Audit pull requests, build & maintain technical documentation
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase 1: Operational CI/CD pipeline on Kubernetes (WP1, WP3-4) • Phase 2: Single-sign-on via SurfConext (WP1), security and privacy audits + monitoring (all WPs) • Phase 3: Deployment and infrastructure documented; support for EOSC and SRC

WP 6:	Project Coordination & Impact Evaluation (Months 1 – 48)
Personnel:	Datta (lead), Emery, Martinovici, van Gils
Consortium partners:	ODISSEI
Goals:	Ensure effective project governance, monitoring, and long-term impact.
Tasks:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manage governance, reporting, and evaluation • Monitor progress, budget, risks, deliverables and institutional use • Collect and incorporate stakeholder feedback • Maintain visibility and strategic alignment
Deliverables:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Phase 1: Governance structure in place; evaluation process launched • Phase 2: Interim report submitted; stakeholder feedback assessed • Phase 3: Final impact report and sustainability roadmap delivered

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4.2 Team composition

ReproHub combines expertise in OS infrastructure ([ODISSEI](#), PI Emery), platform development (PI Datta), and methodology (PI Martinovici + researchers). It leverages development expertise from [tilburg.ai](#) (Datta & van Gils 2025) and strong Tilburg/Erasmus and (inter)national links.

Name, surname	Affiliation	Expertise	Role/contributions
dr. Hannes Datta	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	Digital platforms (lead TSH/tilburg.ai), TSH since 2019	PI, WP6 lead. Strategy/alignment (Tilburg), database/integration (WP3).
dr. Ana Martinovici	RSM ⁴ /ErasmusU	OS practices, reproducibility checks at Psychological Science (STAR editor)	PI, WP1 lead, WP6. Strategy/alignment (ErasmusU), journal liaison.
dr. Tom Emery	ErasmusU, ODISSEI (Exec. Director)	Social science data	PI, WP6. Strategy/alignment (ODISSEI).
Matthijs van Gils	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	Project Manager and product owner tilburg.ai	WP5 lead/product owner, WP6 support.
	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	Data science, software development	Kubernetes & CI/CD (WP5), LLM (WP1), Flask (WP1, 4), FastAPI (WP3).
dr.ir. Stefan Kirsch	TSB/TilburgU ²	Research software and tooling	WP5. Software development and integration.
prof.dr. Tobias Klein	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	Econometrics, reproducibility, TSH since 2019	WP2 lead, provenance logic, execution templates.

dr. Julian Wichmann	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	Browser extension developer	WP3 lead, software specification.
dr. Shrabastee Banerjee	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	OS dissemination, TSH since 2021	WP4 lead, content creation.
dr. Alexander Vossen	JADS ³ , TiSEM/TilburgU ¹	Data science, TSH since 2022	WP1, fine-tuning/testing.
dr. Caspar van Lissa	TSB/TilburgU ² , OS Community Tilburg (Chair), OSC-NL board member	Workflows for open reproducible code in science (WORCS , van Lissa et al. 2021), machine learning	WP2, provenance logic, alignment with WORCS and OSC-NL .
prof.dr. Aurélie Lemmens	RSM ⁴ /ErasmusU, Open and Responsible Science ambassador	Responsible data science, ERIM policy advisor ⁵	WP5, liaison policy at ERIM ⁵ and integration at ErasmusU.
	TiSEM/TilburgU ¹ RSM/ErasmusU ⁴	Development support	Student assistants (SA1-6): guideline curation/testing (WP1), data integration (WP3), content development (WP4), development support (WP5).
dr. Lachlan Deer	U Melbourne	Reproducible workflows, i4r member, TSH since 2021	Former Tilburg/TSH member subcontracted for WP1; alignment international OS network.
¹ Tilburg School of Economics and Management/TilburgU ² Tilburg School of Social and Behavioral Sciences/TilburgU ³ Jheronimus Academy of Data Science, 's-Hertogenbosch ⁴ Rotterdam School of Management/ErasmusU ⁵ Erasmus Research Institute of Management/ErasmusU			

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4.3 Risk management

Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Risk mitigation strategy
IT scalability and security issues	Low	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Committed Azure infrastructure supported by Tilburg LIS & CISO (security) office (BIV classification; availability, integrity & confidentiality). Support from SURF and ODISSEI CTO (Lucas van der Meer). Team/tilburg.ai experienced in CI/CD and AI deployment.
LLM underperforms (WP1)	Medium	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Azure scaling support from Tilburg Digital Research Support Access expert community via Tilburg's AI Special Interest Group (TAISIG) Can queue jobs or throttle user access
LLM privacy concerns from users (WP1)	Medium	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Emphasize open-source LLM and no training from submitted data; wipe data after processing Self-hosting available; open code review Embed in existing reproducibility policies (e.g., Tilburg, ODISSEI) Engage thought leaders, editors, and OS communities via PIs and team members.
Dependency on external parties for adoption (WP1-3)	Low	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strong editorial links via PIs and WP leads (WP1-2) Browser extension exists (Wichmann); will be forked for WP3; commitment Tilburg Library for

and workflow templates (WP2)			pilot + security review; availability for self-installation via browser stores
WP4 materials become outdated	Medium	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use low-maintenance formats for nurturing community contributions • Collaborate with platforms like FORRT • Updates guaranteed for grant period
Coordination challenges due to large team	Medium	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Defined roles and deliverables • Active monitoring by PM and WP leads • Ongoing support from ODISSEI and project controller (Tilburg) to adapt when needed
Difficulty hiring for unfilled positions	Low	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Candidate for RSE1 already identified • Strong network (e.g., eScience Center, Tilburg graduates in data science)

Word count SEC43 (max. 250): 250

4.4 Budget

Position	HOT scale	Institution	Total FTE	Years active	Amount
Researcher and Applicant (Datta)		Tilburg University	0.80	4	€
Researcher and Co-Applicant (Martinovici)		Erasmus University	1.00	4	€
Project Manager (van Gils)		Tilburg University	3.20	4	€
Research software engineer 1 (to be hired)		Tilburg University	2.80	4	€
Research software engineer 2 (Kirsch)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Researcher (Banerjee)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Researcher (Klein)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Researcher (van Lissa)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Researcher (Wichmann)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Researcher (Vossen)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Researcher (Lemmens)		Erasmus University	0.20	4	€
Student assistant 2 (Tilburg)		Tilburg University	0.30	2	€
Student assistant 3 (Tilburg)		Tilburg University	0.40	4	€
Student assistant 5 (Tilburg)		Tilburg University	0.80	4	€

Material/IT Type	Description	Cost calculation	Total (€)
(international) travel and accommodation expenses incl. conference visit	national and international conferences	Participation in three conferences per year (two national at €750 each, one international at €2,500), for 4 years. Different team members may attend each year.	€ 16,000.00
Computing time	compute for WP1/WP5, hosting for WP1 and WP3-4	Hosting costs: €50/month over 48 months for three components (websites for WP1 and WP4, API for WP3). Open-source LLM (scheduled or on-demand): €150/month (year 1), €250/month (years 2–3), €300/month (year 4).	€ 18,600.00
Storage capacity	storage for all WPs	Storage estimate: WP1 (125 GB, LLM + server + 25 replication packages x 50 GB = 1,250 GB), WP2 (25 replication packages x 50 GB = 1,250 GB), WP3 (50 GB, database + server), WP4 (50 GB, platform + server). WP5 and WP6 use institutional OneDrive (in-kind). Total: 2,725 GB x €0.10/month x 48 months.	€ 13,080.00
Software (components); only with open license	web analytics for WP1, WP3, and WP4	Subscription to (open-source) Matomo cloud for web analytics: €75/month x 48 months.	€ 3,600.00
work performed by third parties	subcontracting expenses for WP1 - University of Melbourne	Subcontracting (WP1 – University of Melbourne): ██████████ contribution by Lachlan Deer, covering specification and strategic advice for WP1, collaboration with the Australian Open Science Network, alignment of open science practices beyond the Netherlands, and hosting replication games in partnership with i4r.	€ 46,800.00
work performed by third parties	external designer for WP3 and WP4	Design of browser extension look and feel, including badge (WP3: €1,000); full user interface overhaul for WP4 platform (€5,000).	€ 6,000.00
costs of repositories and data stewardship for long-term storage of data according to FAIR principles	long term storage	Metadata creation and contribution to long-term storage fees to ensure availability of archives on Tilburg's institutional Dataverse, in line with FAIR principles.	€ 1,500.00
knowledge dissemination costs	content promotion on social media	Monthly boosted posts on LinkedIn and Instagram to increase visibility (€50 x 48 months) plus a one-time cost of €600 for creating social media visual assets.	€ 3,000.00
work performed by third parties	student assistants at Erasmus University Rotterdam	Student assistants at Erasmus are hired through an Erasmus subcontractor and therefore budgeted under material costs. For years 1–4: SA1 at 0.2 FTE/year, SA4/SA5 at 0.1 FTE/year, totaling 0.4 FTE/year. Calculation: 0.4 FTE/year x 4 years x €44/hour (HOT scale 2.1–6) x 1,355 hours.	€ 95,392.00

Total Personnel requested:	1.295.922,00 €
Total Material/IT requested:	203.972,00 €
Total budget requested:	1.499.894,00 €

4.5 Budget justification

Personnel

ReproHub brings together researchers, developers, and active OS community members.

Van Gils (.8 FTE) leads **project management**, coordinating the **developer pool** supporting WPs 1–4 and aligning efforts with project strategy/goals (WP6). As head of *tilburg.ai*'s developer team, van Gils brings PM experience integrating with Tilburg's IT infrastructure and close collaboration with **policy and IT staff**.

Two research Software Engineers (RSEs), coordinated by van Gils, implement development tasks in WP5. RSE1 (.7 FTE) contributes expertise in LLMs and Python (Flask/FastAPI), supporting WPs 1-3. RSE2 (Kirsch; 0.1 FTE) supports WP4. Two student assistants (.1–.2 FTE) complement the team, **following the TSH and *tilburg.ai* model** (PI Datta).

PI Martinovici (.25 FTE) leads alignment with research communities. **PI Datta** (.2 FTE) contributes platform development expertise. **ODISSEI supports (in-kind) PI Emery** and existing **ODISSEI staff** (e.g., CTO Lucas van der Meer; communications). **Tilburg University provides in-kind support** through existing staff (e.g., IT research infrastructure, Kitty de Heij; library, Daan Rutten; digital research support (DRS), Jisk Attema).

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Researcher involvement is critical for defining user needs and testing. In WPs 1-4, experienced researchers (0.1 FTE each, 0.05 FTE for Lemmens) collaborate with junior researchers and **student assistants** (0.1–0.2 FTE each; budgeted under material costs at Rotterdam due to contracts).

Material/IT

Costs include **computing** (open-source LLM in WP1, front/backends in WP1, 3 & 4; €18.6k), and **storage** across all WPs (€13k). An external designer (€6k) will create an OS badge for WP3 and a design-overhaul for WP4. Travel (€16k) covers two national and one international conference annually. Deer (€46k, 0.1 FTE) joins WP1 via subcontracting. Formerly at Tilburg and now based in Melbourne, he supports WP1 output quality and international OS alignment. Remaining costs: web analytics (€3.6k), social media dissemination (€3k), long-term storage (€1.5k), and student assistants in Rotterdam (€95k).

Word count SEC45 (max. 300): 300

4.6 Impact plan

ReproHub fosters **scalable impact**—locally, nationally, and globally—through open infrastructure, institutional embedding, and broad community engagement. It delivers **early-stage scientific impact** during the project (e.g., publications using *ReproBuddy*), with **lasting value** beyond the funding period (e.g., *ReproRun* on [EOSC](#)).

Researchers at Tilburg and Erasmus—as **early adopters**—will benefit from integrated workflows, reproducibility support, and training. These **initial use cases** will inform iterative development, while outreach activities within departments, workshops, and integration with DRS **increase visibility/uptake within participating institutions**.

Through **ODISSEI's network**, tools will scale to **45+ institutions** (5000+ researchers). Collaboration with journals (e.g., *Psychological Science*, *The Econometrics Journal*) embeds tools into **peer review processes**, promoting international visibility.

To drive adoption among academic stakeholders, we will give workshops at ODISSEI's Summer School, organize one replication event (with [i4r](#); Deer), present at key conferences (e.g., [SIPS](#), [EMAC](#), [Open Science Festival](#), [SURF Research Day](#)), and share tools/materials with authors via journal networks.

With four deliverables (WP1-WP4), *ReproHub* improves the discoverability and verifiability of open outputs for journalists, policymakers, and citizens. Trusted verification of research results (WP2) further promotes societal trust in science. Communication efforts (€3k) include social media, blogs, and university press channels.

Word count SEC46 (max. 200): 200

Section 5: Sustainability and software management

Section 5.1: Sustainability plan

We aim to sustain long-term usability, reliability, and maintenance of infrastructure developed across work packages by adhering to **best practices for open-source development** (Sonabend et al. 2024), **standardized infrastructure, and institutional embedding**. *ReproHub*, as a **funded part of the ODISSEI network**, will host and evolve the tools as part of its infrastructure, ensuring **relevance beyond the project period**.

Sustainability Efforts During the Project

All tools support interoperability with other OS infrastructures (e.g., SURF Research Cloud, SANE). They will be released under **permissive open-source licenses**, with clear documentation, contribution guidelines, and codes of conduct. Outputs will follow **FAIR** (Barker et al. 2022) and **FAIR-USE4OS principles** (Sonabend et al. 2024) and be hosted on GitHub and mirrored to Zenodo for long-term archiving. We rely on widely adopted technologies and avoid niche dependencies, reducing maintenance costs and promoting reuse.

We commit to **legal and ethical compliance** by aligning WP1 with the EU AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689) and the forthcoming General-Purpose AI (GPAI) Code of Practice. These include risk classification, transparency, and measures for human oversight.

Institutional embedding is facilitated by **DRS's commitment to integrate tools into research support services at Tilburg** (e.g., guidelines on research data management and replication packages) and **Erasmus** (e.g., ERIM, Erasmus Research Services, Rotterdam School of Management's Digitalization & Information Services). Community building and reach (WP4) will support adoption, also by collaborating with **Tilburg University Library staff**.

Future Sustainability

The infrastructure relies on continued access to a compute platform for hosting the open-source LLM and frontend of ReproBuddy (WP1), the API for OpenScienceRadar (WP3), and the website *opensciencehub.nl* (WP4).

ODISSEI has **formally committed to sustaining the project's technical and financial components** beyond the funding period. TSH will be part of **ODISSEI's portfolio of service providers** and supported through its annual budget. **Tilburg University's Library** has also committed to embedding research assistant positions in its operations. In addition, TSH retains €50k in its operational budget for future costs.

We estimate **post-project staffing needs** as follows: 0.5 FTE of senior researchers (e.g., five at 0.1 FTE each), 0.8 FTE of research assistants (two each at Tilburg and Erasmus), 0.1 FTE for a software engineer to maintain backend stability and security, and 0.2 FTE for a community manager to support engagement and onboarding.

Plans to Recover Future Infrastructure Costs

The infrastructure will initially serve **ODISSEI's full-service members**, including users of **CBS data**, the **LISS panel**, and **SoDa**. TSH will pursue **follow-up funding** through national sources like NWO's calls for sustainable research software. Additional cost recovery may come from partnerships with funders and academic journals that provide tools like *ReproBuddy* or *ReproRun* to their communities, via integration or membership-based models (e.g., at SSRN).

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Section 5.2: Software management plan

1. Please provide a brief description of your software, stating its purpose and intended audience.

ReproHub produces **four key infrastructure components** contributing to the visibility and accessibility of open science material and practices at different stages of the research lifecycle:

- **ReproBuddy (WP1):** An AI-powered assistant that provides automated, context-sensitive guidance for improving reproducibility packages. Targeted at researchers, especially those submitting to journals or funding agencies.
- **ReproRun (WP2):** A workflow for automated, secure validation and documentation of results provenance. Designed for researchers working with CBS data or other privacy-sensitive sources.
- **OpenScienceRadar (WP3):** A browser extension that displays open science indicators alongside the search results of academic search engines (e.g., Google Scholar) and publisher pages to improve visibility and discoverability of OS outputs. Intended for students, researchers, and librarians.
- **OpenScienceHub (WP4):** A learning and community platform that extends [Tilburg Science Hub \(TSH\)](#) to national level and hosts FAIR tools and tutorials to support onboarding, documentation, and community engagement.

All software is developed in accordance with recommendations for FAIR software (Maassen et al. 2019), [endorsed](#) among others by NWO, SURF, DANS, and the Software Sustainability Institute, and FAIR-USE4OS (Sonabend et al. 2024). We used the FAIR software checklist (Spaaks et al., version .0.2.2) developed by the Netherlands eScience Center and Australian Research Data Commons for self-assessment.

2. How will you manage versioning of your software?

All infrastructure components will use semantic versioning (e.g., v1.2.3) with clear changelogs maintained in GitHub repositories. Git tags and branches will track stable releases and development progress. CI/CD pipelines (set up in WP5) will automate tagging and deployment processes.

3. How will you make your software publicly available? What license will your software have?

All infrastructure components will be made available on GitHub under the MIT License, a permissive open-source license that allows broad reuse. Each repository will include a LICENSE file, a README, and a CONTRIBUTING.md. Concurrently, software will be catalogued at the European Open Science Cloud ([EOSC](#)).

4. How will users of your software be able to cite your software?

Each stable release of all software components will be archived with a DOI on Zenodo. Citation files (CITATION.cff) will be included in each repository, and the software metadata will follow CodeMeta standards to ensure easy citation by users and integration into citation systems.

5. How will your software be documented? Please describe your plans for: user documentation, documentation for future developers and for installation requirements. Please provide links to documentation if already available.

- **User documentation:** Will be published on *OpenScienceHub* ([opensciencehub.nl](#), WP4) in SEO-optimized format and mirrored to Zendo (FAIR). Content will include use cases, walkthroughs, and hands-on tutorials.
- **Developer documentation:** Will be maintained in each repository, including API references, function-level comments, and development notes.
- **Installation instructions:** Included in each README.md, covering dependencies, setup, and environment configuration. Docker images and setup scripts will be provided throughout.

6. How will contribution guidelines and governance structure of your software be documented?

Each software repository will include a CONTRIBUTING.md describing coding standards, pull request processes, and community expectations. Governance follows an open core model: Core contributors review contributions, with oversight from the PI team and WP leads. A CODE_OF_CONDUCT.md will outline community values.

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7. How will your software be tested?

Each tool will use automated unit and integration tests run through CI pipelines. Tools like *pytest* and Docker-based test environments will be used depending on the component. Manual user testing will also be conducted (e.g., for *ReproBuddy* during AI output validation in WP1). When testing, key user communities at Tilburg (e.g., DRS), Rotterdam (e.g., Erasmus Research Services), and the wider ODISSEI network (e.g., LISS panel, CBS) will be involved.

8. How will you check that it respects the licenses of libraries and dependencies it uses?

All dependencies will be checked using automated license compliance tools. Packages will be audited regularly during CI to ensure license compatibility with the MIT license and compliance with OS standards. Manual checks will also be part of code reviews (WP5, also in guidance by RSE2).

9. How will your software be packaged and distributed?

- **ReproBuddy (WP1):** Hosted service ([SURFconext](#) login), plus a downloadable (dockerized) base version.
- **ReproRun (WP2):** Packaged as Docker containers with downloadable execution templates for common research workflows.
- **OpenScienceRadar (WP3):** Distributed via Chrome/Firefox/Edge/Safari browser stores. Hosted API to serve OS data.
- **OpenScienceHub (WP4):** Delivered as a dynamic site in Python/Flask; dockerized for hosting (and available at [opensciencehub.nl](#)).

10. What level of support will be provided for users of the software and how will this support be organized?

Users will receive tiered support:

- **Self-service:** Public tutorials, FAQs, and example workflows on [opensciencehub.nl](#).
- **Community:** GitHub Issues for bugs and suggestions.
- **Institutional:** Dedicated support via research support staff at Tilburg, Erasmus, and ODISSEI.

11. How do you plan to ensure long term maintenance of your software?

ODISSEI has **formally committed to supporting the infrastructure beyond the funding period** (see sustainability plan). TSH will be integrated into ODISSEI's portfolio of services and financially supported through its annual budget cycle. Tilburg University Library will embed additional RA positions. Code will remain open source, modular, and hosted via GitHub and archived at Zenodo. Community contribution models and partnerships (e.g., with journals) will further extend the sustainability of tools like *ReproBuddy* and *ReproRun*.

Section 6: References

- ALLEA. (2023). *The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – Revised Edition 2023*. Berlin. <https://doi.org/10.26356/ECOC>
- Barker, M., Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez-Ortiz, C., Psomopoulos, F., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., & Honeyman, T. (2022). Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 622. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>
- Cadwallader, L., & Hrynaszkiewicz, I. (2022). A survey of researchers' code sharing and code reuse practices, and assessment of interactive notebook prototypes. *PeerJ*, 10, e13933. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.13933>
- Datta, H., & van Gils, M. (2025). *Annual Report of tilburg.ai (2024/2025) (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15231645>
- Dwork, C., & Roth, A. (2014). The algorithmic foundations of differential privacy. *Foundations and Trends® in Theoretical Computer Science*, 9(3–4), 211–407. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/04000000042>
- European Union (2024). *Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 (Artificial Intelligence Act)*. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>
- Ferguson, J., Littman, R., & Pezzuto, J.-H. (2023). Survey of open science practices and attitudes in the social sciences. *Nature Communications*, 14(1), 5401. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-41111-1>
- General-Purpose AI (GPAI) Code of Practice. (2025, March 11). *Third draft*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/third-draft-general-purpose-ai-code-practice-published-written-independent-experts>
- Hardwicke, T. E., Thibault, R. T., Kosie, J. E., Wallach, J. D., Kidwell, M. C., & Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2022). Estimating the prevalence of transparency and reproducibility-related research practices in psychology (2014–2017). *Perspectives on Psychological Science*, 17(1), 239–251. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1745691620979806>
- Katz, D. S., & Chue Hong, N. P. (2024). Special issue on software citation, indexing, and discoverability. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 10, e1951. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1951>
- Van Lissa, C. J., Brandmaier, A. M., et al. (2021). WORCS: A workflow for open, reproducible code in science. *Data Science*, 4(1), 29–49. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-210031>
- Maassen, J., Hof, C. H. J., Martinez Ortiz, C., & Spaaks, J. (2019). *Five Recommendations for FAIR Software*. <https://fair-software.eu>
- Netherlands Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. (2018). <https://doi.org/10.17026/dans-2cj-nvwu>
- NPOS. (2022). *Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda (Approved version)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>
- NWO. (2025). *Sharing research data and software: How are NWO and ZonMw funded projects doing?* NWO News. <https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/sharing-research-data-and-software-how-are-nwo-and-zonmw-funded-projects-doing>
- Research Software Alliance. (2024). *[ADORE] Amsterdam Declaration on Funding Research Software Sustainability (1.1)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13735888>
- Sonabend, R., Gruson, H., Wolansky, L., Kiragga, A., & Katz, D. S. (2024). FAIR-USE4OS: Guidelines for creating impactful open-source software. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 20(5), e1012045. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1012045>
- Spaaks, J. H., Honeyman, T., & Verhoeven, S. *FAIR software checklist (Version 0.2.2)* [Computer software]. <https://github.com/ardc-fair-checklist/ardc-fair-checklist.github.io>
- Trisovic, A., Lau, M. K., Pasquier, T., & Crosas, M. (2022). A large-scale study on research code quality and execution. *Scientific Data*, 9(1), 60. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01143-6>

Section 7: Declaration

By submitting this form, I declare that:

- I and all the individuals involved in this proposal satisfy the nationally and internationally accepted standards for scientific conduct as stated in the Netherlands [Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#) (The Universities of the Netherlands).
- The research organisation has been informed of this grant application and the research organisation accepts the grant conditions of this programme.
- I have completed this application form truthfully.
- I have submitted a pre-proposal for this Call for proposals in ISAAC.